

Deliverable D2.1

Statistical downscaling of climate projections

www.moirai-project.eu

22 April 2026

Author: NOA

Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact mitigation.

Research and Innovation Action under EC Horizon Europe
Grant Agreement no. 101180994

Project coordinator:
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION (NTUA),
Greece

Deliverable 2.1
Statistical downscaling of climate projections

Start date of project: 01 November 2024

Duration: 42 months

Due date of deliverable: 31 April 2026

Actual submission date: 30 April 2026

Lead beneficiary for preparing the deliverable:

Ethino Asteroskopeio Athinon (NOA)

Person-months used to produce deliverable:

14.5 (total contributors see def. next page)

Authors:

Konstantinos V. Varotsos, Ioannis Lemesios, Georgios Katavoutas, Myrto Gratsea, Christos Giannakopoulos

Version	DATE	CHANGE RECORDS	Responsible
0.1	dd.mm.yyyy	Template	EurOcean
0.2	22.04.2026	Draft submitted to WP lead	NOA
0.3	28.04.2026	Reviewed deliverable	WP lead
0.4	29.04.2026	Final version submitted to Coordination Team after revision based on WP lead review	NOA
1.0	30.04.2026	Reviewed Final version submitted to EC	Coordination team

Approval	Date: dd.mm.yyyy	Sign.
		Coordinator signature

USED PERSON-MONTHS FOR THIS DELIVERABLE					
No	Beneficiary	PM	No	Beneficiary	PM
1	NTUA		9	FONDAZIONE CMCC	
2	DMI		10	HCMR	
3	BSC CNS		11	EII	
4	ENEA		12	INFERENCE	
5	AWI		13	USC	
6	CSIC		14	EUROCEAN	
7	AU		15	KERT	
8	NOA	14.5			

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the statistical downscaling framework developed in MOIRAI Task 2.1 for the generation of climate-scale atmospheric forcing and ocean boundary-condition datasets from coarse-resolution CMIP6 climate projections. The work addresses the need for high-resolution climate information suitable for driving the regional ocean model configurations of the project across the Mediterranean/Black Sea, Baltic/North Sea, and Arctic/North Atlantic domains. Because raw global climate-model output is too coarse in space and too limited in temporal detail for direct regional application, the deliverable focuses on the development of a statistically robust and operationally feasible framework for translating global climate projections into datasets that are structurally compatible with regional ocean modelling requirements.

The methodology consists of two complementary branches. For the atmospheric component, daily fields from the CMIP6 model MPI-ESM1-2-LR are first spatially regridded and bias-adjusted against high-resolution regional reanalyses using the CDF-t method. They are then temporally disaggregated to a 3-hourly resolution using a machine-learning framework based on XGBoost, trained on regional reanalysis data. This branch was developed for 2 m air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, mean sea level pressure, downward shortwave radiation, downward longwave radiation, and 10 m wind components. For the ocean component, monthly CMIP6 fields of temperature, salinity, sea surface height, and current components are horizontally regridded, vertically mapped where needed to the target depth structure, and bias-adjusted against regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products.

The results presented in the report indicate that the atmospheric downscaling framework can generate high-resolution 3-hourly forcing fields with coherent spatial structure, seasonally plausible behaviour, and physically consistent variable-specific characteristics. The illustrative results shown in the deliverable correspond to one representative test year, 2014, selected to demonstrate the behaviour of the framework across the three MOIRAI domains. These examples show that the method is capable of preserving the large-scale daily climate signal while reconstructing plausible sub-daily

variability suitable for climate-scale ocean-forcing applications. At the same time, the results make clear that the atmospheric products are not intended to reproduce the exact chronology of short-lived weather events, especially for variables whose sub-daily variability is dominated by synoptic dynamics, such as mean sea level pressure.

For the ocean branch, the indicative examples show that the downscaling framework can generate monthly boundary-condition datasets that preserve the broad temporal evolution of the original climate projections while improving consistency with the target regional reference products and depth structure. The results for temperature and salinity indicate that the CDF-t adjustment modifies the mean state while retaining the long-term projected tendency. For ocean the current components, the adjustment is also applied consistently across depth levels, although the interpretation of annual mean signals is less direct because of their smaller magnitude and stronger interannual variability. Unlike the atmospheric illustrations, which are shown for a single test year, the statistically downscaled ocean datasets are available for the full 1971–2100 period through the MOIRAI data portal.

Overall, this deliverable establishes the current scientific and technical basis for statistical downscaling within MOIRAI. The developed framework is designed to provide climate-scale initial conditions, boundary conditions, and atmospheric surface forcing for regional ocean modelling related to climate change. Its purpose is not to replace reanalysis-based reconstructions, but to produce physically plausible, bias-adjusted, and structurally compatible input datasets that preserve the projected large-scale climate signal and can support the simulation of future marine conditions and climate risks across the main MOIRAI domains.

Acknowledgements:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction	12
2 Objectives and scope	13
3 Study domains, datasets and variables	15
3.1 Study domains	15
3.2 Climate projection data	15
3.3 Reference datasets for atmospheric variables	16
3.4 Reference datasets for ocean variables	16
3.5 Variables considered	16
4 Methodology	18
4.1 Atmospheric variables	18
4.1.1 Spatial statistical downscaling	18
4.1.2 Temporal disaggregation to 3-hourly resolution	20
4.1.3 Variable-specific implementation	22
4.2 Ocean variables and boundary conditions	25
4.2.1 Input ocean variables and reference datasets	25
4.2.2 Horizontal regridding	26
4.2.3 Vertical mapping to target depth levels	26
4.2.4 Bias adjustment	26
5 Results	28
5.1 Atmospheric downscaling results	28
5.1.1 Near-surface air temperature	28
5.1.2 Relative humidity	31
5.1.3 Other atmospheric variables	34
5.2 Ocean boundary-condition downscaling results	42
5.2.1 Temperature and salinity	42
5.2.2 Current components and sea surface height	45
6 Discussion	49
6.1 Main strengths of the framework	49
6.2 Key limitations and challenges	50
6.3 Implications for regional ocean modelling under climate change	51
7 References	52
8 Concluding remarks	53

Table of Figures

Figure 4.1 Example of atmospheric spatial statistical downscaling for annual mean 2 m air temperature over the Mediterranean domain in 2014. The panels compare the raw regridded CMIP6 field and the corresponding CDF-t bias-adjusted field.	17
Figure 4.2 Downscaled 3-hourly 2 m temperature generated using Random Forest (RF) and XGBoost (XGB) for the period 1971–2100. Insets show the corresponding evaluation of both machine-learning methods against CERRA over 1985–2014.	19
Figure 5.1 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly 2 m air temperature over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	26
Figure 5.2 Same as Figure 5.1, but for the Baltic/North Sea domain.	27
Figure 5.3 Same as Figure 5.1, but for the Arctic/North Atlantic domain.	28
Figure 5.4 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly relative humidity over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	29
Figure 5.5 Same as Figure 5.4, but for the Baltic/North Sea domain.	30
Figure 5.6 Same as Figure 5.4, but for the Arctic/North Atlantic domain.	31
Figure 5.7 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly precipitation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	32
Figure 5.8 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly downward shortwave radiation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	33
Figure 5.9 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly downward longwave radiation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	34
Figure 5.10 Comparison of diurnal anomaly evolution in mean sea level pressure between CERRA and the XGBoost reconstruction for selected days over the Mediterranean domain. The figure illustrates the difficulty of reproducing the exact intra-day synoptic evolution of pressure fields from daily bias-adjusted climate-model input.	36
Figure 5.11 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly 10 m wind speed over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.	37

- Figure 5.12 Indicative example of annual mean sea water potential temperature at selected depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area. 39
- Figure 5.13 Indicative example of annual mean salinity at selected depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area. 40
- Figure 5.14 Indicative example of annual mean zonal current component at selected upper-ocean depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area. 42
- Figure 5.15 Indicative example of annual mean meridional current component at selected upper-ocean depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area. 43

1 Introduction

High-resolution climate information is needed to drive regional and coastal ocean models and to support climate-risk analyses in marine environments. However, raw global climate-model output is generally too coarse in space and too limited in temporal detail to be used directly for these purposes. This is especially important in regions such as the Mediterranean/Black Sea, the Baltic/North Sea, and the Arctic/North Atlantic, where coastlines, land–sea contrasts, and regional circulation patterns strongly affect the atmosphere–ocean system.

Within MOIRAI, Task 2.1 addresses this gap through the statistical downscaling of climate projections for the main regional domains of the project. The work presented in this deliverable consists of two complementary components. The first concerns atmospheric variables and follows a spatio-temporal framework in which daily CMIP6 projections are spatially downscaled, bias-adjusted, and temporally disaggregated to 3-hourly resolution. The second concerns ocean variables used as boundary conditions, for which monthly CMIP6 fields are horizontally regrided, vertically mapped where needed, and bias-adjusted against regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products.

The overall aim is to generate datasets that are structurally compatible with the regional ocean model configurations while preserving the large-scale climate signal of the driving global projections. For the atmospheric branch, this means producing 3-hourly forcing fields suitable for climate-scale ocean simulations. For the ocean branch, it means preparing monthly boundary-condition datasets consistent with the target horizontal and vertical model structure.

This deliverable documents the datasets, methodology, implementation, and current results of the Task 2.1 downscaling work, covering both atmospheric forcing and ocean boundary conditions for the MOIRAI regional domains.

2 Objectives and scope

The main objective of Task 2.1 is to generate high-resolution climate projections for key atmospheric and ocean variables required to support the regional ocean modelling activities of MOIRAI. In the Description of the Action, the task is defined as the statistical downscaling of climate projections for use as input to the physical and biogeochemical modelling systems developed in WP2 and WP3, with outputs intended to provide both atmospheric surface forcing and ocean boundary conditions.

More specifically, the work presented in this deliverable has four main objectives. First, it aims to develop a statistical framework for the spatial downscaling and bias adjustment of coarse-resolution CMIP6 climate projections over the main MOIRAI regional domains. Second, it aims to reconstruct sub-daily atmospheric variability from daily climate projections in order to generate 3-hourly forcing fields suitable for ocean simulations. Third, it aims to produce spatially consistent and bias-adjusted ocean fields that can be used as lateral boundary conditions for the regional ocean model configurations. Fourth, it aims to assess the current maturity, strengths, and limitations of the proposed methodology for climate-scale forcing applications.

The scope of the deliverable covers two complementary methodological branches. The first branch concerns atmospheric variables and includes the generation of high-resolution spatio-temporal projections for 2 m air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, mean sea level pressure, downward shortwave and longwave radiation, and 10 m wind components. The second branch concerns ocean variables and includes the statistical downscaling of sea water potential temperature, salinity, sea surface height, and horizontal current components for use as ocean boundary conditions.

Geographically, the work addresses the three main MOIRAI domains: the Mediterranean/Black Sea, the Baltic/North Sea, and the Arctic/North Atlantic. In the present phase, the atmospheric downscaling framework has been developed using CERRA as a reference over the Mediterranean/Black Sea and Baltic/North Sea, and CARRA-WEST over the Arctic/North Atlantic. For the ocean boundary-condition

component, the methodology uses regional CMEMS reanalysis products as references for each area of interest.

In terms of temporal and scenario coverage, the current implementation is based on historical and SSP3-7.0 CMIP6 simulations from MPI-ESM1-2-LR, with the overall projection horizon extending to 2060 in line with the current Task 2.1 setup. For the atmospheric component, the statistical framework combines daily bias-adjusted climate projections with machine-learning-based temporal disaggregation to 3-hourly resolution. For the ocean component, the processing is performed at monthly resolution and focuses on the preparation of boundary-condition datasets on the target reanalysis grids and depth structure.

This deliverable is therefore methodological and scientific in nature. Its main purpose is to document the datasets, workflow, implementation choices, and current results obtained so far, rather than to present a final, fully operational multi-model production system. At the same time, the results reported here establish the scientific and technical basis for the generation of climate-scale forcing datasets to be used in the subsequent regional ocean modelling phases of MOIRAI.

3 Study domains, datasets and variables

3.1 Study domains

The statistical downscaling framework was developed for the three main MOIRAI regional domains: the Mediterranean/Black Sea, the Baltic/North Sea, and the Arctic/North Atlantic. These domains correspond to the principal regional-sea systems addressed in the project and span a broad range of climatic, oceanographic, and coastal conditions relevant for climate-risk assessment and regional ocean modelling.

From the perspective of statistical downscaling, these domains also provide a useful basis for evaluating the transferability of a common methodological framework across contrasting environments. The Mediterranean/Black Sea domain is characterized by strong land-sea thermal contrasts and marked regional gradients, the Baltic/North Sea domain by shallow shelf-sea dynamics and strong air-sea coupling, and the Arctic/North Atlantic domain by the additional complexity associated with high latitudes, sea-ice influence, and strong spatial heterogeneity.

3.2 Climate projection data

The climate projection data used in the current implementation originate from the CMIP6 global climate model MPI-ESM1-2-LR (ensemble member r1i1p1f1). For the atmospheric branch, daily climate fields were used as the starting point for the spatio-temporal downscaling framework. For the ocean branch, monthly three-dimensional fields were processed to produce statistically downscaled ocean boundary conditions. The work was developed using historical and SSP3-7.0 simulations, with projection data extending to 2060 in line with the current Task 2.1 implementation.

The source model resolution is $1.875^\circ \times 1.875^\circ$, which is far coarser than the spatial scales required by the MOIRAI regional applications. This mismatch motivates the need for statistical downscaling and bias adjustment before the data can be used as forcing for regional ocean simulations.

3.3 Reference datasets for atmospheric variables

High-resolution regional reanalysis datasets were used as references for the atmospheric downscaling. For the Mediterranean/Black Sea and Baltic/North Sea domains, the Copernicus European Regional Reanalysis (CERRA) was used. CERRA provides 3-hourly atmospheric fields at approximately 5.5 km horizontal resolution and serves as the benchmark for both the spatial bias adjustment and the reconstruction of sub-daily variability.

For the Arctic/North Atlantic domain, the reference dataset is CARRA-WEST, the western-domain component of the Copernicus Arctic Regional Reanalysis, which provides atmospheric fields at 3-hourly temporal resolution and approximately 2.5 km horizontal spatial resolution.

3.4 Reference datasets for ocean variables

For the ocean boundary-condition component, the reference datasets are regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products (CMEMS), selected separately for each domain in order to ensure consistency with the large-scale oceanographic characteristics of the regional seas. For the Mediterranean open boundaries, the Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish Ocean Physics Reanalysis is used. For the Baltic/North Sea region, the Atlantic-European North West Shelf Ocean Physics Reanalysis is used. For the Arctic domain, the Arctic Ocean Reanalysis is used.

These products provide the horizontal grid structure, depth levels, and distributional reference needed for the regridding and bias adjustment of the monthly CMIP6 ocean variables. Their use allows the downscaled ocean fields to be aligned with the spatial and vertical structure required by the regional ocean modelling systems.

3.5 Variables considered

The atmospheric variables considered in the present deliverable are those required to generate surface forcing for the ocean simulations. They include 2 m air temperature, relative humidity, total precipitation, mean sea level pressure, downward shortwave radiation, downward longwave radiation, and the zonal and meridional 10 m wind components.

The ocean variables considered are those required to construct statistically downscaled lateral boundary conditions for the regional ocean model setups. They include sea water potential temperature, sea water salinity, sea surface height, and the zonal and meridional current components. For the three-dimensional variables, both horizontal and vertical consistency with the regional reference datasets are required, whereas for sea surface height, only horizontal remapping and bias adjustment are needed.

Taken together, these datasets and variables define the scientific and technical basis of the Task 2.1 downscaling activity reported in this deliverable.

4 Methodology

The methodology developed in Task 2.1 consists of two complementary branches. The first generates high-resolution atmospheric forcing from daily CMIP6 projections through spatial downscaling, bias adjustment, and temporal disaggregation to 3-hourly resolution. The second prepares monthly ocean boundary conditions through horizontal regridding, vertical mapping where needed, and bias adjustment against regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products. Together, these components provide the workflow used to translate coarse-resolution climate projections into datasets compatible with the requirements of the MOIRAI regional ocean model configurations.

4.1 Atmospheric variables

For the atmospheric component, the framework was developed to generate high-resolution 3-hourly forcing fields from daily CMIP6 climate projections. Daily outputs from MPI-ESM1-2-LR under historical and SSP3-7.0 conditions were used, with CERRA as reference over the Mediterranean/Black Sea and Baltic/North Sea domains and CARRA-WEST over the Arctic/North Atlantic domain. The atmospheric variables considered include 2 m air temperature, relative humidity, total precipitation, mean sea level pressure, downward shortwave and longwave radiation, and the zonal and meridional 10 m wind components. The workflow consists of two steps: spatial statistical downscaling of daily climate fields and temporal disaggregation from daily to 3-hourly resolution.

4.1.1 Spatial statistical downscaling

In the first step of the atmospheric workflow, the daily CMIP6 climate-model fields were spatially downscaled to the target high-resolution regional grids. The original MPI-ESM1-2-LR outputs were first bilinearly interpolated from the native global model grid to the corresponding CERRA or CARRA-WEST grid over each MOIRAI domain. After regridding, the daily fields were bias-adjusted using the CDF-t method, with the regional reanalysis datasets serving as reference (Figure 4.1). CDF-t was selected for the bias adjustment step because it is better suited than standard Quantile Mapping methods for climate-change applications. In a recent perfect-model experiment for European temperature and precipitation, Vrac et al. (2025) showed that although Quantile Mapping and CDF-t

perform similarly over the calibration period, important differences emerge in future projections: standard Quantile Mapping introduced biases in the mean, standard deviation, and extremes and did not adequately preserve the climate-change signal, whereas CDF-t and its variants showed smaller biases and provided a more reliable framework for adjustment in a climate-change context. This procedure was applied for the full 1971–2100 period and was designed to correct systematic biases in the statistical distributions of the climate-model variables while preserving the long-term climate-change signal of the original projections. In this way, the output of the spatial downscaling step consists of daily bias-adjusted atmospheric fields at the spatial resolution of the target regional datasets, providing the basis for the subsequent reconstruction of sub-daily variability.

Figure 4.1 Example of atmospheric spatial statistical downscaling for annual mean 2 m air temperature over the Mediterranean domain in 2014. The panels compare the raw regrided CMIP6 field and the corresponding CDF-t bias-adjusted field.

4.1.2 Temporal disaggregation to 3-hourly resolution

Following the spatial statistical downscaling step, the daily bias-adjusted atmospheric fields were temporally disaggregated to 3-hourly resolution in order to generate forcing suitable for the regional ocean simulations. This step is required because the climate projections used as input are available at daily time resolution, whereas the regional ocean modelling systems require sub-daily atmospheric forcing in order to represent the temporal evolution of surface fluxes and momentum forcing more realistically. The temporal disaggregation was therefore designed to reconstruct large-scale 3-hourly

variability while remaining consistent with the daily climate signal of the bias-adjusted projections.

To develop this component of the framework, several machine-learning and deep-learning methods were evaluated using high-resolution reanalysis data for the period 1985–2014. The dataset was split into a training period (1985–2008, 80%) and an independent evaluation period (2009–2014, 20%). The tested methods included Support Vector Regression, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and a feed-forward Neural Network with two hidden layers. The comparison showed that all methods achieved comparable skill during evaluation, but XGBoost was selected for operational implementation because it provided a favorable balance between predictive performance, computational efficiency, and scalability for large-domain applications (Figure 4.2).

It should be noted that satisfactory statistical performance at an individual grid point does not by itself guarantee feasibility for regional-scale application. In principle, one could calibrate a separate model for each grid cell, but such an approach would be computationally demanding and difficult to maintain for multi-variable, multi-domain, and multi-decadal production workflows. The methodological choice in Task 2.1 was therefore guided not only by pointwise predictive skill, but also by the need for computational efficiency, robustness, and scalability over large domains. In this context, XGBoost was considered a suitable compromise between model performance and practical applicability for the generation of climate-scale 3-hourly forcing fields.

The selection of XGBoost is also consistent with recent downscaling-related studies. Sebbar et al. (2023) applied XGBoost to the machine-learning-based downscaling of hourly ERA5-Land air temperature over mountainous regions and reported strong performance relative to alternative methods. In addition, Georgiades et al. (2025) used an XGBoost model to temporally downscale daily climate data to hourly values in order to generate high-temporal-resolution projections of heat stress. Although these studies do not implement exactly the same daily-to-3-hourly forcing reconstruction framework adopted here, they nevertheless support the broader suitability of XGBoost for climate and meteorological downscaling applications.

In the adopted framework, XGBoost learns normalized sub-daily anomalies from the reanalysis data and transfers this information to the daily bias-adjusted climate projections in order to generate 3-hourly variability. In other words, the method does not attempt to predict arbitrary sub-daily values independently from the daily climate signal; instead, it reconstructs 3-hourly anomalies around the daily mean value provided by the bias-adjusted projections. This formulation helps preserve daily consistency while reconstructing plausible large-scale sub-daily variability of the main atmospheric forcing fields. At the same time, it implies that the reconstructed 3-hourly fields tend to be spatially smoother than the original reanalysis and are therefore more suitable for climate-scale forcing applications than for the explicit representation of short-lived, high-intensity atmospheric extremes.

Figure 4.2 Downscaled 3-hourly 2 m temperature generated using Random Forest (RF) and XGBoost (XGB) for the period 1971–2100. Insets show the corresponding evaluation of both machine-learning methods against CERRA over 1985–2014.

4.1.3 Variable-specific implementation

Although the same general machine-learning framework was applied to all atmospheric variables, the final implementation was adapted for each variable in order to reflect differences in physical behavior, predictor structure, and the constraints required for a stable reconstruction of 3-hourly variability. In all cases, the models were trained using 3-hourly regional reanalysis data over the training period, using CERRA for the Mediterranean/Black Sea and Baltic/North Sea domains and CARRA-WEST for the

Arctic/North Atlantic domain, and were then applied to the bias-adjusted daily climate projections across the MOIRAI regions.

Near-surface air temperature

Near-surface air temperature was reconstructed as a realistic 3-hourly evolution around the daily thermal background provided by the bias-adjusted climate projections. The method uses the daily mean, minimum, and maximum temperature fields as the main predictors and learns how the sub-daily temperature cycle evolves within each day. In this way, the reconstructed 3-hourly values remain constrained by the daily climate signal while still reproducing a plausible diurnal cycle. Several variable-specific adjustments were introduced to improve realism and temporal continuity. In particular, the timing of the temperature cycle was represented using local solar time rather than UTC, so that the phase of the diurnal cycle better follows the longitudinal position of each grid point. In addition, a midnight blending procedure was applied to reduce artificial discontinuities at day boundaries, and the daily input files were aligned to midnight before projection to the 3-hourly timeline. Further consistency checks were included to keep the reconstructed temperatures close to the daily minimum and maximum values and to suppress unrealistic oscillations when the daily temperature range is very small.

Relative humidity

Relative humidity was reconstructed within the daily humidity envelope defined by the bias-adjusted climate projections. The method uses the daily mean, minimum, and maximum relative humidity fields as the main predictors and learns how sub-daily humidity variations evolve within each day. A shifted projection of the daily humidity statistics, together with a midnight blending procedure, was used to reduce artificial discontinuities at day boundaries. Additional consistency checks were imposed to maintain physical coherence between daily minimum, mean, and maximum humidity values and to keep the reconstructed 3-hourly fields within realistic bounds. Cases with very small daily humidity range were treated by suppressing unnecessary sub-daily oscillations and reverting toward the daily mean. In this way, the reconstructed humidity

fields remain tied to the daily moisture conditions while still reproducing a plausible sub-daily cycle.

Precipitation

Precipitation required a stricter formulation, because the reconstructed 3-hourly series had to remain fully consistent with the bias-adjusted daily precipitation total. The method uses the daily precipitation amount together with daily humidity indicators and seasonal and hourly information to learn how rainfall is typically distributed within the day. The machine-learning model was therefore used to estimate the sub-daily distribution, after which the resulting 3-hourly values were renormalized so that their sum matched the daily total exactly at each grid cell. In addition, dry days were explicitly forced to zero precipitation, thereby avoiding spurious drizzle and improving physical consistency. This setup allows the model to reconstruct plausible intra-day rainfall timing while preserving the daily water balance.

Shortwave radiation

Downward shortwave radiation was treated differently because its sub-daily evolution is strongly controlled by solar geometry. Rather than asking the machine-learning model to learn the full diurnal cycle from scratch, the implementation used the cosine of the solar zenith angle as a deterministic predictor and allowed XGBoost to learn a modulation factor representing the sub-daily shape around the daily mean. This design reduces the burden on the machine-learning model because the basic astronomical structure of the diurnal cycle is prescribed explicitly, while the model only needs to learn how atmospheric conditions modulate that structure. Additional constraints were imposed so that nighttime values remain zero and the daily mean of the reconstructed 3-hourly series remains equal to the input daily mean. A day-wise renormalization step was also included to ensure exact consistency with the bias-adjusted daily radiative forcing.

Longwave radiation

In contrast to shortwave radiation, downward longwave radiation has a much weaker deterministic diurnal structure. Its reconstruction was therefore based more directly on

learned sub-daily anomalies around the daily mean radiative background provided by the bias-adjusted climate projections. In this case, the machine-learning model learns a normalized sub-daily shape relative to the daily mean longwave radiation, so that the reconstructed 3-hourly values remain explicitly constrained by the daily forcing signal. Additional safeguards were introduced to remove unrealistic spikes, avoid non-physical values, and maintain consistency with the imposed daily mean. In practice, the reconstruction was bounded within physically plausible ranges and normalized so that the daily longwave forcing remained preserved.

Mean sea level pressure

Mean sea level pressure required additional stabilization because it is governed mainly by synoptic-scale evolution rather than by a strong regular diurnal cycle. The machine-learning model learns a normalized sub-daily shape relative to the daily mean pressure, so that the reconstructed 3-hourly fields remain anchored to the daily large-scale state. To ensure temporal stability, the daily values were projected to the 3-hourly timeline using a shifted day definition, and a midnight blending step was applied to reduce discontinuities at day boundaries. Further post-processing was introduced to suppress rare unphysical spikes, including clipping anomalous departures from the daily baseline and applying a short temporal smoothing to the anomaly component while leaving the daily mean unchanged.

Wind components

The zonal and meridional 10 m wind components were reconstructed using a formulation centred on the daily mean wind state provided by the bias-adjusted climate projections. The method uses the daily mean wind speed together with the daily mean zonal and meridional components as predictors and learns how the sub-daily structure of each wind component evolves within the day. For both components, the reconstruction was formulated relative to the daily mean value, which allows the 3-hourly series to remain consistent with the large-scale daily circulation while still representing intra-day variability. This approach is particularly useful for wind components because they are

signed variables and therefore require a formulation that can preserve both magnitude and direction. By combining daily wind speed information with the daily zonal and meridional components, the framework provides a more stable representation of the evolving wind vector than would be obtained by reconstructing each component independently from time information alone.

4.2 Ocean variables and boundary conditions

For the ocean component, the statistical downscaling framework was developed to generate monthly boundary-condition datasets from coarse-resolution CMIP6 climate projections for use in the regional ocean model configurations of MOIRAI. In contrast to the atmospheric branch, this framework does not involve temporal disaggregation to sub-daily resolution, but instead focuses on horizontal regridding, vertical mapping to the target depth structure, and bias adjustment against regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products. The methodology was applied to ocean temperature, salinity, sea surface height, and current components.

4.2.1 Input ocean variables and reference datasets

For the ocean boundary-condition component, the starting point consists of monthly CMIP6 ocean fields from MPI-ESM1-2-LR under historical and SSP3-7.0 conditions. The variables considered include sea water potential temperature, salinity, sea surface height, and the zonal and meridional current components. These variables were selected because they provide the large-scale thermodynamic and dynamic information required for the preparation of lateral ocean boundary conditions for the regional model configurations.

The reference datasets are regional Copernicus Marine reanalysis products, selected separately for each MOIRAI domain in order to match the large-scale oceanographic characteristics of the target regional seas. For the Mediterranean open boundaries, the reference product is the Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish Ocean Physics Reanalysis. For the Baltic/North Sea region, the Atlantic-European North West Shelf Ocean Physics Reanalysis is used. For the Arctic domain, the Arctic Ocean Physics Reanalysis is used.

These products provide the target horizontal grid, the target depth structure, and the reference statistical distributions required for the subsequent downscaling steps.

4.2.2 Horizontal regridding

In the first processing step, the monthly CMIP6 ocean fields were horizontally regridded from the native global model grid to the target CMEMS latitude–longitude grid for each regional domain. This step was required because the coarse-resolution CMIP6 ocean output is not directly compatible with the grid structure used by the regional ocean reanalysis products and downstream modelling systems. Bilinear interpolation was applied to transfer the large-scale spatial patterns of the original model fields to the target regional grid while maintaining a smooth representation of the ocean state. This horizontal remapping was performed for all ocean variables considered in the boundary-condition framework, including temperature, salinity, current components, and sea surface height.

4.2.3 Vertical mapping to target depth levels

For the three-dimensional ocean variables, horizontal regridding alone was not sufficient, because the CMIP6 model output and the CMEMS regional products also differ in their vertical discretization. A dedicated vertical mapping step was therefore applied in order to align the regridded CMIP6 fields with the target CMEMS depth structure. For each target depth level, the nearest corresponding depth level from the global climate model output was assigned, thereby preserving the large-scale vertical structure of the projected fields while ensuring compatibility with the depth coordinates required by the regional ocean models. This step was applied to sea water potential temperature, salinity, and the zonal and meridional current components, whereas sea surface height, being a two-dimensional field, did not require vertical remapping.

4.2.4 Bias adjustment

After horizontal regridding and, where needed, vertical mapping, the monthly ocean fields were bias-adjusted against the corresponding CMEMS regional reanalysis products using the CDF-t method. The correction was applied independently at each horizontal grid point and, for three-dimensional variables, at each depth level. This

approach was adopted in order to reduce systematic distributional biases while preserving the projected long-term climate-change signal of the original CMIP6 simulations. In this way, the downscaled ocean fields remain consistent with the projected temporal evolution while better matching the statistical characteristics of the regional reference datasets. The final outputs consist of monthly bias-adjusted ocean fields on the horizontal grid and depth structure of the selected CMEMS products, prepared for sea water potential temperature, salinity, zonal and meridional current components, and sea surface height. These datasets are intended for use as lateral boundary conditions in the MOIRAI regional ocean model configurations.

5 Results

This section presents the current results of the statistical downscaling framework developed in Task 2.1 for both atmospheric forcing and ocean boundary conditions. The results are intended to illustrate the behavior, consistency, and current maturity of the methodology across the main MOIRAI domains, rather than to provide an exhaustive validation of every variable and configuration. Emphasis is placed on representative examples that demonstrate the spatial structure of the downscaled products, the consistency of the reconstructed temporal variability, and the suitability of the resulting datasets for climate-scale regional ocean modelling applications.

5.1 Atmospheric downscaling results

The atmospheric downscaling framework produced high-resolution 3-hourly fields for the main surface-forcing variables required by the regional ocean simulations. The results presented below focus first on near-surface air temperature, which provides one of the clearest examples of the behaviour of the spatio-temporal downscaling framework, and then summarize the corresponding performance for the other atmospheric variables. The objective of this section is to illustrate the spatial coherence, seasonal behaviour, and practical suitability of the reconstructed forcing fields across the Mediterranean/Black Sea, Baltic/North Sea, and Arctic/North Atlantic domains. In general, these products are intended for climate-scale forcing applications, meaning that they aim to preserve the large-scale daily climate signal and generate physically plausible sub-daily variability, rather than to reproduce the exact chronology and structure of every short-lived weather event.

5.1.1 Near-surface air temperature

Near-surface air temperature provides one of the clearest examples of the behaviour of the spatio-temporal downscaling framework developed in Task 2.1. Because its sub-daily evolution is strongly linked to the daily thermal state and to the diurnal cycle, temperature is particularly well-suited for illustrating how the combination of spatial statistical downscaling and machine-learning-based temporal disaggregation can generate physically plausible 3-hourly forcing fields from daily climate projections. Representative

examples of the downscaled 3-hourly 2 m air temperature fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 are shown for the Mediterranean/Black Sea (Figure 5.1), Baltic/North Sea (Figure 5.2), and Arctic/North Atlantic (Figure 5.3) domains. In the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain, the figures show a clear north–south thermal gradient, with warmer conditions over North Africa and the southern Mediterranean and lower temperatures farther north and over elevated terrain. In the Baltic/North Sea domain, they show the expected contrast between milder maritime areas and colder northern and inland sectors, especially in the winter case. In the Arctic/North Atlantic domain, the panels show a marked contrast between the cold Greenland sector and the relatively warmer surrounding oceanic regions. The selected cases also show a seasonally coherent evolution through the year, with distinctly colder winter conditions and warmer summer conditions across all three domains.

XGBoost t2m — 6 random days in 2014 at 12:00 UTC

Figure 5.1 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly 2 m air temperature over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

Figure 5.2 Same as Figure 5.1, but for the Baltic/North Sea domain.

XGBoost t2m — 6 random days in 2014 at 12:00 UTC

Figure 5.3 Same as Figure 5.1, but for the Arctic/North Atlantic domain.

5.1.2 Relative humidity

Relative humidity provides a useful complementary example of the spatio-temporal downscaling framework, because its sub-daily evolution is constrained by the daily moisture conditions while remaining sensitive to regional atmospheric structure and seasonal changes. The reconstructed 3-hourly relative humidity fields show coherent spatial patterns across the Mediterranean/Black Sea, Baltic/North Sea, and Arctic/North Atlantic domains, while remaining within physically realistic bounds imposed by the daily humidity envelope. Representative examples of the downscaled 3-hourly relative humidity fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 are shown in Figure 5.4, Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6. In the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain, the figures show lower humidity over the southern continental margins and higher humidity over the sea and the northern parts of the domain. In the Baltic/North Sea domain, they show persistently high

humidity over broad marine and northern areas, with weaker gradients than in the Mediterranean. In the Arctic/North Atlantic domain, the panels show very high humidity over large oceanic sectors together with more localized contrasts near Greenland and adjacent coastal regions. The seasonal progression is also plausible, with relatively lower humidity over warmer southern land areas in summer and broader regions of elevated humidity during autumn and winter, particularly in the northern domains.

Figure 5.4 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly relative humidity over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

Figure 5.5 Same as Figure 5.4, but for the Baltic/North Sea domain.

XGBoost rh — 6 random days in 2014 at 12:00 UTC

Figure 5.6 Same as Figure 5.4, but for the Arctic/North Atlantic domain.

5.1.3 Other atmospheric variables

Precipitation

Precipitation is one of the most demanding variables for temporal disaggregation, because the reconstructed 3-hourly values must remain fully consistent with the bias-adjusted daily precipitation total while still producing plausible intra-day variability. Representative examples of the downscaled 3-hourly precipitation fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain are shown in Figure 5.7. The figure shows that most of the domain remains dry in many of the selected cases, while precipitation is concentrated in localized patches rather than spread unrealistically across the whole basin. In particular, wet areas are confined to limited sectors in the northern and eastern parts of the domain on several dates, whereas large parts of the

Mediterranean remain at or near zero precipitation. This behaviour is consistent with the intermittent and spatially heterogeneous nature of precipitation. An important feature of the implementation is that the daily precipitation amount is conserved exactly at each grid cell, so that the 3-hourly distribution modifies only the timing of rainfall within the day and not the daily water balance.

Figure 5.7 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly precipitation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

Shortwave radiation

Downward shortwave radiation provides a particularly informative example of the atmospheric downscaling framework because its sub-daily evolution is strongly constrained by solar geometry while still being modulated by atmospheric conditions. Representative examples of the downscaled 3-hourly shortwave radiation fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain are shown in

Figure 5.8. The figure clearly shows the seasonal increase from the February and November cases to the June and August cases, with much higher noon shortwave radiation during summer. It also shows a pronounced north–south gradient, with the highest values over the southern Mediterranean and North African sectors and lower values over the northern parts of the domain. In addition, several panels display spatial variability associated with atmospheric modulation superimposed on the broader astronomical control of the diurnal cycle. This behaviour is consistent with the adopted implementation, in which the basic daily cycle is prescribed through solar geometry, and the machine-learning model reconstructs the sub-daily modulation around the daily mean. An important feature of the implementation is that nighttime values are kept at zero, and the daily mean radiative input remains consistent with the bias-adjusted daily forcing.

XGBoost ssrd — 6 random days in 2014 at 12:00 UTC

Figure 5.8 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly downward shortwave radiation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

Longwave radiation

Downward longwave radiation provides a useful contrast to shortwave radiation because its sub-daily evolution is less directly controlled by solar geometry and is more closely linked to the daily thermal and moisture state of the atmosphere. Representative examples of the downscaled 3-hourly longwave radiation fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain are shown in Figure 5.9. The figure shows lower longwave radiation in the winter case and distinctly higher values during the June and August cases, consistent with warmer atmospheric conditions in summer. It also shows broad and smooth regional gradients, with higher values over warmer southern sectors and weaker, less sharply structured contrasts than in the shortwave radiation fields. This behaviour agrees with the adopted implementation, in

which the reconstruction is based on learned sub-daily anomalies around the daily mean radiative background while preserving consistency with the daily forcing signal.

Figure 5.9 Spatio-temporally downsampled 3-hourly downward longwave radiation over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

Mean sea level pressure

Mean sea level pressure represents one of the most challenging variables for the temporal disaggregation framework. The reconstruction is conditioned on daily bias-adjusted fields, while the sub-daily variability is statistically reconstructed using an XGBoost model trained on CERRA reanalysis for the period 1985–2014. Because the available predictor information is limited to the daily scale, the exact intra-day synoptic evolution, including the propagation and timing of pressure systems, cannot be uniquely recovered. This limitation is particularly relevant for mean sea level pressure, which is primarily governed by synoptic-scale atmospheric dynamics and does not exhibit a

strong regular diurnal cycle, unlike variables such as near-surface air temperature or downward shortwave radiation. It is also important to note that the 2014 fields shown here belong to the bias-adjusted GCM simulation, which forms part of a continuous free-running climate simulation covering 1971–2060, with historical forcing up to 2014 and SSP3-7.0 thereafter. Although bias-adjusted, this simulation is not synchronized with the chronology of observed weather events in 2014. The comparison in Figure 5.10 shows that the CERRA anomalies evolve substantially within the day, with changing centres and gradients across the Mediterranean domain. By contrast, the reconstructed fields are much smoother and do not reproduce the same sequence of synoptic anomaly patterns. The comparison, therefore, highlights a structural limitation of the method for pressure, rather than a failure in variables for which the sub-daily cycle is more directly constrained by daily predictors.

Figure 5.10 Comparison of diurnal anomaly evolution in mean sea level pressure between CERRA and the XGBoost reconstruction for selected days over the Mediterranean domain. The figure illustrates the difficulty of reproducing the exact intra-day synoptic evolution of pressure fields from daily bias-adjusted climate-model input.

Wind components

The wind reconstruction is intended to provide physically plausible 3-hourly surface-momentum forcing consistent with the daily large-scale circulation state of the bias-adjusted climate projections. A representative view of the resulting near-surface wind forcing is provided by the reconstructed 10 m wind speed fields at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014 over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain in Figure 5.11. The figure shows enhanced wind speeds over marine corridors and open-water sectors, while lower values are found over many surrounding continental areas. It also shows that the location and intensity of the stronger-wind regions vary between the selected dates, indicating that the framework produces regionally structured and temporally varying wind fields rather than a static wind pattern. Because the reconstruction is based on the daily mean wind speed together with the daily zonal and meridional components, the resulting fields are consistent with the daily wind state while still representing plausible intra-day variability.

XGBoost WS10 — 6 random days in 2014 at 12:00 UTC

Figure 5.11 Spatio-temporally downscaled 3-hourly 10 m wind speed over the Mediterranean/Black Sea domain at 12:00 UTC for six selected days in 2014.

5.2 Ocean boundary-condition downscaling results

The ocean downscaling framework was applied across multiple boundary areas relevant to the MOIRAI regional model configurations. Because the full set of outputs spans several domains, variables, and depth levels, the figures presented here are intended as indicative examples illustrating the behaviour of the method rather than as an exhaustive presentation of all generated boundary-condition datasets; some variables, such as sea surface height, are described in the text without separate illustrative figures. The emphasis is placed on representative cases that demonstrate the effect of the regridding and CDF-t adjustment on the mean state, the preservation of the long-term temporal evolution, and the vertical consistency of the resulting monthly ocean fields. Additional boundary locations and depth levels were processed using the same workflow, but only a subset is shown here for clarity.

5.2.1 Temperature and salinity

Sea water potential temperature provides one of the clearest examples of the behaviour of the ocean boundary-condition downscaling framework. The indicative depth-resolved annual mean time series shown here correspond to representative boundary areas and selected depth levels and illustrate the typical behaviour of the method across the available MOIRAI ocean configurations (Figure 5.12). In these examples, the temperature series show a persistent long-term warming throughout the upper ocean, with positive trends evident across the selected levels. At the same time, the CDF-t-adjusted series are generally cooler than the corresponding regridded fields, indicating that the statistical correction mainly affects the mean state while preserving the long-term warming tendency of the original projection. This behaviour can be seen both in the near-surface layers and in the deeper levels for which valid boundary-condition data are available. The results, therefore, suggest that the temperature adjustment modifies the background thermal structure in a physically consistent way without removing the projected climate signal.

A similar interpretation applies to salinity, although the sign of the long-term tendency differs from that of temperature (Figure 5.13). The indicative salinity series shows a gradual decrease across the selected depth levels, while the CDF-t-adjusted fields remain close to the regridded series and mainly apply a moderate correction to the mean level. In the upper and intermediate layers, the adjusted salinity retains the same broad temporal evolution as the regridded field, indicating that the statistical correction does not distort the large-scale projected tendency. Taken together, the temperature and salinity results show that the combined regridding, vertical mapping, and CDF-t adjustment framework is able to produce vertically consistent three-dimensional ocean fields while preserving the long-term temporal evolution needed for climate-scale lateral boundary forcing.

Figure 5.12 Indicative example of annual mean sea water potential temperature at selected depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area.

Figure 5.13 Indicative example of annual mean salinity at selected depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area.

5.2.2 Current components and sea surface height

The zonal and meridional current components, together with sea surface height, complete the set of downscaled monthly ocean boundary-condition variables. Their interpretation is less straightforward than for temperature and salinity because the annual mean current components are generally smaller in magnitude, more sensitive to local circulation structure, and more strongly affected by interannual variability. The indicative figures shown here for the zonal (Figure 5.14) and meridional (Figure 5.15) current components are therefore presented primarily to illustrate the effect of the statistical adjustment across depth levels rather than to provide a detailed assessment of long-term circulation trends for every boundary location.

For both current components, the annual mean series show that the CDF-t adjustment is applied consistently through the vertical structure of the boundary-condition fields. In the representative examples shown here, the statistical correction modifies the mean level of the current components more clearly than their long-term trend, while preserving the overall magnitude and temporal variability of the regridded series. This behaviour is visible in both the zonal and meridional components, where the adjusted and regridded fields remain dynamically comparable but differ in their background state. Such behaviour is expected, because the purpose of the correction is to improve consistency with the regional reference products rather than to impose a strong deterministic trend structure on variables whose annual means are small and highly variable.

Sea surface height, although not shown here, was processed with the same general statistical downscaling framework. In this case, only horizontal regridding and bias adjustment were required, since no vertical remapping is involved. The resulting monthly sea surface height fields form part of the final boundary-condition dataset and contribute to the dynamical consistency of the regional ocean forcing. Together with temperature, salinity, and current components, they complete the set of downscaled ocean variables produced for the MOIRAI regional model configurations.

Figure 5.14 Indicative example of annual mean zonal current component at selected upper-ocean depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area.

Figure 5.15 Indicative example of annual mean meridional current component at selected upper-ocean depth levels, comparing regridded and CDF-t-adjusted monthly boundary-condition fields over 1971–2100 for a representative boundary area.

6 Discussion

The results presented in Section 5 indicate that the statistical downscaling framework developed in Task 2.1 provides a scientifically consistent basis for generating atmospheric and ocean datasets for the MOIRAI regional ocean simulations. An important point in interpreting these results is that the produced datasets are not intended as stand-alone meteorological or oceanographic reconstructions. Rather, they are designed to serve as **climate-scale initial and boundary conditions** for regional ocean modelling applications focused on climate change. This intended use is essential for understanding both the strengths and the limitations of the framework.

6.1 Main strengths of the framework

A first strength of the methodology is that it addresses, within a common framework, the two main classes of input required by the regional ocean models: atmospheric surface forcing and ocean boundary conditions. This is a major practical advantage for MOIRAI, because the regional ocean configurations require datasets that are not only physically plausible in isolation, but also structurally compatible across variables, domains, and temporal scales. By combining statistical downscaling, bias adjustment, temporal reconstruction for the atmospheric component, and regridding and vertical remapping for the ocean component, the framework provides a coherent processing chain from coarse-resolution CMIP6 climate projections to regionally usable forcing products.

A second strength is that the framework is explicitly designed to preserve the large-scale climate signal of the driving global climate model. For the atmospheric variables, the results show that the daily bias-adjusted climate signal is retained while plausible 3-hourly variability is reconstructed at the target regional resolution. For the ocean variables, the results indicate that the regridding and CDF-t adjustment can modify the mean state and improve consistency with the reference products while preserving the broad long-term temporal evolution of the original projections. This is particularly important in a climate-change context, where the central requirement is not exact reconstruction of historical weather or ocean events, but the generation of dynamically and statistically consistent datasets that retain the projected long-term signal.

A third strength is the practical scalability of the approach. In the atmospheric branch, the choice of XGBoost reflects a balance between predictive skill, computational efficiency, and applicability over large domains and long periods. In the ocean branch, the workflow is transparent and transferable, relying on a sequence of horizontal regridding, vertical mapping, and bias adjustment steps that can be reproduced for multiple boundary areas and configurations. This gives the framework value not only as a scientific exercise, but also as an operational basis for producing forcing datasets for the project simulations.

6.2 Key limitations and challenges

At the same time, the results make clear that the framework has important limitations directly related to its intended use. For the atmospheric component, the temporal reconstruction is conditioned on daily fields. This means that the exact timing, propagation, and internal evolution of short-lived atmospheric systems cannot, in general, be recovered uniquely. This limitation is particularly evident for mean sea level pressure, whose sub-daily variability is governed mainly by synoptic-scale dynamics and is not strongly constrained by a regular diurnal cycle. It is also relevant for precipitation, where the method can distribute the daily total into plausible 3-hourly amounts while preserving the daily water balance, but is not expected to reproduce the detailed structure of short-lived convective events.

For the ocean component, the limitations are different. The bias-adjusted boundary-condition fields are not intended to reproduce the exact chronology of the observed ocean state, but to provide climate-consistent, dynamically usable boundary information for regional model integrations. The indicative temperature and salinity results suggest that the main projected temporal tendencies are retained, while the mean state is corrected toward the regional reference datasets. However, for the current components, the interpretation is less direct because annual mean currents are smaller in magnitude, more variable, and more sensitive to location and depth. In these cases, the main value of the correction lies in improving consistency of the background state

and maintaining vertically coherent forcing, rather than in yielding easily interpretable long-term trend signals.

A further challenge concerns the balance between physical realism and methodological tractability. The adopted framework is designed for multi-domain, multi-variable, and multi-decadal applications. This makes it scientifically useful and operationally feasible, but it also means that some simplifications are unavoidable. The resulting products are therefore best understood as statistically adjusted climate-forcing datasets that are suitable for driving regional ocean models in climate-change experiments, rather than as exact replications of observed atmospheric and oceanic evolution.

6.3 Implications for regional ocean modelling under climate change

These characteristics are consistent with the role of Task 2.1 within MOIRAI. The purpose of the downscaled datasets is to provide initial and boundary conditions and, for the atmospheric component, surface forcing, for regional ocean modelling experiments that investigate climate-change impacts and future marine conditions. In that context, the most important requirement is not exact event-by-event agreement with historical reanalysis, but the generation of fields that are physically plausible, regionally compatible, and consistent with the long-term climate signal of the driving projections. For regional ocean modelling related to climate change, this is a critical distinction. Ocean-model sensitivity to forcing often depends more on the realism of the large-scale thermodynamic and dynamic background state, the preservation of long-term tendencies, and the internal consistency among variables than on the exact chronology of individual historical weather systems.

Overall, the results obtained so far indicate that the Task 2.1 methodology meets this objective in a scientifically meaningful way. It provides a robust basis for producing the atmospheric and ocean datasets required by the MOIRAI modelling chain, while also making clear where caution is needed in the interpretation of variables that are especially sensitive to short-timescale dynamics.

7 Concluding remarks

This deliverable presented the statistical downscaling framework developed in MOIRAI Task 2.1 for the generation of climate-scale atmospheric forcing and ocean boundary-condition datasets from CMIP6 climate projections.

For the atmospheric component, the results presented in this deliverable are based on one representative test year, 2014, which is used to illustrate the behaviour of the spatio-temporal downscaling framework across the Mediterranean/Black Sea, Baltic/North Sea, and Arctic/North Atlantic domains. These examples show that the framework can generate high-resolution 3-hourly forcing fields with coherent spatial structure, seasonally plausible behaviour, and variable-specific characteristics that are consistent with the intended use of the products as climate-scale surface forcing for regional ocean modelling. At the same time, the results also make clear that the atmospheric products should not be interpreted as exact reconstructions of the chronology of short-lived weather events, especially for variables whose sub-daily variability is strongly governed by synoptic dynamics.

For the ocean component, the methodology was applied to the preparation of statistically downscaled monthly boundary-condition datasets for temperature, salinity, current components, and sea surface height. In contrast to the atmospheric examples, which are illustrated here for a single test year, the ocean datasets are available for the full 1971–2100 period. The indicative results shown in this report demonstrate that the ocean framework preserves the broad temporal evolution of the original climate projections while improving consistency with the target regional reference products and depth structure. These datasets are intended to support climate-change-oriented regional ocean modelling by providing boundary fields that are physically plausible, vertically consistent, and aligned with the target model grids.

Overall, the work reported here establishes the current scientific and technical basis for statistical downscaling within MOIRAI. The results indicate that the Task 2.1 framework is capable of delivering both atmospheric forcing and ocean boundary-condition products suitable for use as climate-scale initial conditions, boundary conditions, and

surface forcing in the regional ocean simulations of the project. In this sense, the framework is not designed to replace reanalysis-based reconstructions, but to provide climate-consistent input datasets for investigating future marine conditions and climate-change impacts across the main MOIRAI domains.

8 References

- Vrac, M., Loukos, H., Noël, T., and Defrance, D.: Should We Use Quantile-Mapping-Based Methods in a Climate Change Context? A “Perfect Model” Experiment, *Climate*, 13, 137, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli13070137>.
- Sebbar, B. E., et al.: Machine-Learning-Based Downscaling of Hourly ERA5-Land Air Temperature over Mountainous Regions, *Atmosphere*, 14, 610, 2023.
- Georgiades, P., Economou, T., Proestos, Y., Araya, J., Lelieveld, J., and Neira, M.: Global projections of heat stress at high temporal resolution using machine learning, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 17, 1153–1171, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-1153-2025>.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S): Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (CERRA), CERRA sub-daily regional reanalysis data for Europe on single levels, Climate Data Store.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S): Copernicus Arctic Regional ReAnalysis (CARRA), Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1991 to present, Climate Data Store.
- Copernicus Marine Service: Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish – Ocean Physics Reanalysis, product ID IBI_MULTIYEAR_PHY_005_002, DOI: 10.48670/moi-00029.
- Copernicus Marine Service: Atlantic-European North West Shelf – Ocean Physics Reanalysis, product ID NWSHELF_MULTIYEAR_PHY_004_009, DOI: 10.48670/moi-00059.
- Copernicus Marine Service: Arctic Ocean Physics Reanalysis, product ID ARCTIC_MULTIYEAR_PHY_002_003, DOI: 10.48670/moi-00007.

MOIRAI

This report is made under the project
Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact
mitigation (MOIRAI).

Funded by
the European Union

Project partners:

